

Makerspace in Poverty Communities: Maker Culture and its Impact on the New Generation

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Abstract

The present proposal has the objective to be a "culture developer" and develop the current stage of potential technical and technology and the meeting of knowledge between IFES-Cariacica high school students and young people enrolled in fundamental schools of this municipality to project a creative insertion in the contemporary world of work. As specific structured objectives, in addition to a literature review on the relationship between technique, technology, knowledge, and bioethics in the 21st century, develop work with students who graduated in Production Engineering and Management Technicians to disseminate Maker Culture in public schools. Municipalities of the Cariacica city; Present the possibilities of 3D Printing for students and teachers, besides the concrete exercise of its use; and transform IFES Cariacica Makerspace into a training space for a new mindset for children and youth impacting the learning culture. Participatory research was carried out in 14 municipal schools in Cariacica, involving a total audience of 601 people. Lectures and workshops were held using computers and 3D printers, where participants accessed existing technologies at the institution to learn about, produce, and demonstrate viable future processes for work experiences. The activities will be conducted by students from the Integrated Technical Management Course and the Production Engineering Bachelor course at the IFES Cariacica campus. The results will be obtained through groups focused on the research subjects after workshops, where they will be allowed to capture as possible transformers that occurred after the project. Throughout the project, IFES Cariacica Maker Space will be open to municipal schools, creating a reference place, among others, for rapid protection and 3D printing.

Keywords: Makerspaces; Engineering Education; Maker; 3D printing.

1 Framework

Cupani (2011), while discussing the complex and ambiguous relationship between reflection and action, manifested both in technique and technology, asserts that: "What seems to unite ancient and modern forms of technology (...) is the circumstance that they represent manifestations of the human capacity to make things. Also, all production, technical or technological, manifests knowledge. The capacity to make things means the capacity to produce the difference from the capacity to act, that is, to lead one's own life (instead of living purely instinctively). By making, man originates artifacts, artificial objects or processes".

Engineering presents itself as a historical process that demarcates, in various times and spaces, the creative, projecting, and open to the new production inherent to the human condition. In this sense, for those of us who, as teachers, technology presents itself as an open field for reflection, whether on its use or appropriation, but essentially on the human values behind the said phase of social production of life. Technology is a daily presence in teaching through the devices available in consumer society. Still, it only presents itself as a potential for dreams in the student universe if linked to the perspective of teaching and work.

As educators, we know that there is no education without reflection and that anxieties are overcome as changes in scenarios within the field of work open their horizons to the new and renew the daily routine of educational action based on new or renewed experiences socialized in various parts of the world. Action in teaching is linked to continuous concern about students' future and the instruments available to provide a creative,

innovative, and student-centered education. In this sense, the sciences of technology and philosophy intersect as thinking about life and materializing new material/sensory meanings for present and future generations becomes a point of reference in constant movement from what is understood by education in general and institutionalized education in particular.

According to the "*Anuário Brasileiro da Educação Básica*," 2018, of the almost 49 million people inserted in this educational scope, nearly 40 million are in the public education system. Within this, there are approximately 6 million in early childhood education, 23 million in elementary education, 7 million in high school, 3 million in Youth and Adult Education, 1 million in vocational education, and 46 thousand in unique/specialized schools. These numbers call us to think about this majority universe of young people enrolled in elementary education who will not necessarily present themselves as potential students in the Brazilian public high school. The Federal Institute of Education IFES, with its techniques, technologies, and knowledge, is a national power that materializes this insertion as a future space for the work life of a significant part of the 23 million people enrolled in the Basic Education network.

Also, according to the Yearbook (2018), regarding the Socioeconomic Level (SES), those in conditions ranging from very low to medium within the public network correspond to more than 16 million people, a predominantly young audience. This allows us to reflect on the era of access in consumption, but not necessarily in conscious use to produce always open creative possibilities. It is from this ambiguous coexistence between the most advanced technological era and the multiple facets of despair that haunt youth that we understand the centrality of the role of IFES in society and of the techniques and technologies it possesses and should be available to this group so that their dream universes can be re-signified.

In this sense, the present proposal, covered by documented reflections from the science, technology, and society field, has as its territory a concrete realization of the experience of IFES-Cariacica's action with the public municipal schools of this same municipality. Our 15-year tenure as faculty in the Engineering and Administration courses and fieldwork experiences have required deep reflection on the redefinition of education in the 21st century from the field of bioethics. In the words of Mitcham (1994, cited by Cupani 2011): "The humanities, or philosophy, which could also be called the hermeneutics of technology, seek, by contrast, an understanding of the meaning of technology - its relationship with the trans-technical: art and literature, ethics and politics; religion. It typically begins with non-technical aspects of the human world and considers how technology can (or cannot) adapt or correspond to them" (p. 27).

From this relationship between education committed to the territory and the potential advancement of access to technique as knowledge available to society, these fields merge in the experience of IFES-Cariacica, in general, and the Engineering and Administration courses, in particular. Over the past 13 years, the Federal Institute of Education IFES, Cariacica Campus, has stood out in offering education and preparation for the world of work to the city's residents and its surroundings in the Greater Vitória region.

Considering concrete action in the territory, this research also aims to elucidate the relevance of this category - territory - in light of the teachings of Milton Santos, one of the excellent references in the debate on the space-time technique from a humanistic perspective of geography. For Santos & Becker (2007): "territory is not only the set of superimposed systems of things; territory must be understood as territory used, not the territory itself. The used territory is the ground plus identity. Identity is the feeling of belonging to what belongs to us. The territory is the foundation of work; the place of resistance, material and spiritual exchanges, the exercise of life" (p. 23).

In approaching its context, IFES-Cariacica regularly carries out a project called "Open Doors," where municipal schools from Cariacica visit the IFES facilities to uncover study possibilities and the selection process. Over the

past four years, it was possible to perceive that many students from these schools did not register for the selection process because a "complex of inferiority" was part of the culture of the municipality's students. Opinions such as:

- "I am not good enough to study at IFES";
- "Only those who can afford the preparatory course enter IFES";
- "IFES is a very distant dream";
- "Those who study at IFES must be happier."

As part of the work of the responsible team, students were encouraged to register for the selection process during the visit, and the accompanying teachers began to guide the registrations. The already perceived result is that students who participated in the "Open Doors" project are gradually becoming students at IFES on various Campuses. As proof of the importance of dissemination and approach to IFES society, we have the fact that in the current academic year, 2023-2024, the residents of Cariacica represent 47.85% of the campus students. The project in question was not the only factor but made a significant contribution. From it, the need for greater interaction with the schools of Cariacica was also noticed.

Another project on campus, as an activity of the Administration course, in partnership with Junior Achievement, is the Mini-Company Project. This project, which encourages the formation of an entrepreneurial culture, has been demonstrating over the past four years that students who make up the so-called "Generation Z" respond well to the calls of Do It Yourself (DIY) proposals, which is a determining component of the Maker Culture, which in turn is derived from accessibility to rapid manufacturing and prototyping machines that drive the so-called "Industry 4.0".

From these two experiences, it was possible to observe that the students of Cariacica admire the IFES Institution. However, their belief that accessing it is difficult prevents them from daring to try. Students who enter IFES prefer practical activities as a form of learning.

Our intention, over the four years we will have to study and reflect on the ambiguities and potentialities of the theme, is part of these two inseparable scopes: a) future public of IFES from the presentation, with the protagonist of high school and undergraduate students, of the courses and projects we have; b) in the action of high school and undergraduate education and their relationships with society - Cariacica - the provision of techniques and technologies that open horizons of meaning to youth about their future work environment.

In the scope of the IFES-Community relationship in Cariacica, we understand that the use and provision of technology (Additive Manufacturing) can be an excellent reflective exercise on the conditions of creativity and ingenuity of the region's youth. Socializing access and democratizing knowledge and skills that often only inhabit the imagination of children and adolescents become one of the premises to be reflected and deepened in the study over the following years of postgraduate education.

In this sense, as a basis for understanding, we can comprehend that digital manufacturing, once restricted only to companies and large product developers, has evolved widely thanks to technological advances that could be perceived at various distinct stages and sometimes concomitant over time. Evolution in software and hardware brought more powerful and accessible computers to the public; simultaneously, in telecommunications, the internet was born, and with it came the digital revolution in manufacturing, where access to information was facilitated, and thus, the public began to be able to design their products and produce them (Gershenfeld, 2007).

Termed "digital manufacturing," this new production method makes the end user more active in the production process. They build precisely what they need without the intermediary of any company, and waiting for delivery is often long and frustrating (Igoe & Mota, 2011).

An intrinsic practice to digital manufacturing is Do It Yourself (DIY)." This expression refers to entrepreneurial, creative, and innovative behaviors that have the potential to develop and improve people's learning abilities. It is believed that when this practice is encouraged in an environment with tools that enable prototyping, significant progress, and innovations can be obtained in how products are created and developed (Eychenne & Neves, 2013).

Laboratories that provide digital manufacturing began to appear in the early 2000s, and the most emblematic and well-structured one was the Fabrication Laboratory or Fab Lab. One of the several names given to environments with this purpose is Maker Space, where users are encouraged to create various types of products through their development in a virtual environment through specific software and subsequently their production, either by 3D printing, milling, cutting, or whatever equipment is available in that environment (Gershenfeld, 2007).

DIY practices are closely linked to Makerspaces since enthusiasts find everything they need to develop their projects in these laboratories. Another attractive factor to this audience is that these places, among other characteristics, are zero-cost or affordable to their users (Gershenfeld, 2007).

Roslund and Rodgers (2014) define makerspaces as places where people gather to produce things. These spaces can focus on electronics, robotics, woodworking, laser cutting, programming, or a combination of these activities.

One of the most significant advantages and attractions of digital manufacturing laboratories and maker spaces is that people can imagine a product and have it in their hands moments later. Even if they are not experts in prototyping, the technical staff available in the laboratories can assist less experienced users in their projects (Troxler, 2010).

Exploring this resource type in an educational environment opens broad possibilities for innovation in student learning processes. Education, in general, long stagnated by passive methodologies, can take advantage of these new tools, allowing students to create prototypes to solve real problems. This is revolutionary in learning, research, and technological innovation.

For students to be able to deal with new technologies considering social, ethical, environmental, and economic aspects, the teaching staff of their educational institution must be adequately prepared to stimulate their skills through a methodology that accompanies these new global trends. For all this to be possible, schools must commit to providing physical structure so that the entire learning process is effective (Masson et al., 2012).

Project-Based Learning (PBL) provides integral and gradual learning through practice and continuous challenges. Its development originated in the 1900s with the philosopher John Dewey, who proved it through his students by "learning by doing," valuing them, contextualizing them, and questioning them progressively to solve real problems in projects related to the contents of the study areas, where experimental activities were fundamental (Ribeiro & Mizukami, 2004).

The essence of the Maker Space is closely linked to PBL, as both seek the construction of knowledge through interactions with the environment and proposed challenges, stimulating creativity and problem-solving skills. This idea is also reflected in constructivism, which explains how individuals build and develop knowledge through investigations, activities, dynamics, and interactions with the resources around them. Constructivist theories argue that knowledge does not exist absolutely, but the progress made through global perception, integration of knowledge, and relationship with the environment can bring new possibilities to students (Markham et al., 2008).

PBL has been one of the leading centers of discussion in approaching more active learning and innovative teaching practices. Considered an alternative learning of the current century, it demands more dedication from teachers and students to be efficient. Teachers must change their traditional role as experts in a subject to learning coaches. Similarly, students must exert more effort and understand that knowledge will only be obtained through dedication (Campos, 2011).

Another relevant aspect related to Maker Spaces and active learning methodologies is the acronym STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Math). These learning spaces have substantially supported the formation of a new mindset in students, generating interest and curiosity that allow a greater connection with science, technology, engineering, and mathematics. Martinez and Stager (2013) point out that this educational perspective will become decisive for economic progress, and these skills will be fundamental in global competitiveness.

For the "academy" to modify the traditional teaching model and improve it for a new reality that follows new global and technological trends, it is necessary to invest in laboratories adequately equipped for such feats. Maker Spaces brings this reality to educational institutions in an innovative and accessible way.

2 Research objectives

The primary purpose of this work is to elucidate how the "maker culture" and the current stage of technique and technology enhance the exchange of knowledge among high school students in Administration and undergraduate Engineering students at IFES-Cariacica and young people enrolled in schools in this municipality, aiming to concretely project a creative insertion into the contemporary world of work. To achieve this, the following objectives are intended:

- Study the reality of the region to which IFES-Cariacica belongs, considering an actual study on youth, their level of education, and school dropout rates, using the methodology of focus groups linked to PBL.
- Develop a project with students, administration technicians, and undergraduate Engineering students to disseminate the Maker Culture in public municipal schools in Cariacica.
- Present the possibilities of 3D printing to students and teachers, in addition to the practical exercise of its use.
- Foster a future perspective for young Engineering, Science, Technology, and Mathematics students.
- Transform the Maker Space at IFES-Cariacica into a center for shaping a new mindset for the child and adolescent audience, impacting the learning culture.

3 Methodology

The main aim of this work has been to determine to what extent the maker culture associated with PBL methodology and contemporary techniques and technologies available at IFES-Cariacica allow us to redefine the role of education in the territory as a meeting of knowledge in the service of providing accurate and creative opportunities for youth in their future integration into the world of work.

Conceived to carry out interventions in the institutions that will serve as the research field, this project initially assumed qualitative characteristics regarding its nature and exploratory in terms of its type. It used action research as the research method and focus groups as data collection instruments. Regarding the Action Research method, as defined by Thiollent (1988), "it is a type of social research based on empirical evidence that is conceived and carried out in close association with an action or resolution of a collective problem, in

which researchers and participants representing the situation or problem are involved cooperatively or participatively" (p.14).

According to Gil (2010), this method is more challenging to present in temporally ordered phases. However, as described in the next paragraph, the present research involved researchers, a team of students, teachers, and school management professionals in direct and active contact to disseminate and implement maker culture, making this method appropriate.

Focus groups are a method that allows data collection through interviews conducted by a moderator (MATTAR, 1996). This method generates hypotheses and will complement the Action Research process. Focus groups will be where the perceptions of the actors involved in the research will be detailed and, according to observations, measured to indicate the impact and effectiveness of the activities carried out.

The research field was the Maker Space, located at the Federal Institute of Espírito Santo, Cariacica campus, and Municipal Schools in the City of Cariacica, where 9th-grade students and teachers will be invited to participate in the research process. Throughout the process, the research may also take on characteristics of Extension.

Within the possible limits of the moment, the end activities of this project consist of three phases: researcher and team training, field trips to conduct workshops in municipal schools in Cariacica, which will constitute the research field and guidance and collection of perceptions from those involved.

The following procedures were implemented to systematize the work proposal to achieve the objectives.

Phase 1. Considering the project's resource viability definition, students from the Technical Course in Administration and the bachelor's degree in production engineering were trained, along with IFES teachers, to carry out the proposed activities. They became proficient in using software and manipulating 3D printers and received training to present workshops to the target audience.

Concurrently, the Maker Space underwent adjustments and modifications to be used by the team constantly and subsequently serve the external public. The directors of the municipal schools will be invited to IFES for a project presentation. The schools will be selected based on accessibility and availability.

At the end of this phase, a pilot activity should take place in one of the schools.

Phase 2. After the pilot activity is carried out and evaluated, actions will focus on the other schools to be served. During regular IFES class hours, the students involved will continue to use the Maker Space, developing skills and producing pieces on 3D printers that will be distributed as gifts and incentives to students from municipal schools during workshops. Workshops will last for 3 hours, in addition to 1 hour of lecture, which did not necessarily have to take place on the same day but should precede the workshop.

IFES teachers will talk to teachers and directors of schools to present the possibilities of using the IFES Maker Space by school students on scheduled visits.

Phase 3. The team's collection of perceptions from the visited schools characterizes this stage.

Through the conduct of focus groups, it was identified how the project impacted the school through questions such as:

- How much did the experience change students' perception of their school environment?
- What is the perception of managers and directors about the applicability of technology in their classes?

This project focused on municipally managed schools, which have fewer resources and need more significant support for fostering students' expectations and motivations.

The research field will be the IFES Cariacica campus and its Maker Space for training those involved and use by students. In addition to the Municipal Elementary Schools in Cariacica, it focuses on the 9th grade through lectures and workshops.

4 Results

The results presented here represent a part of the scope of this research. We chose to present the entire proposal to facilitate understanding of the context. The study is ongoing, and new data will be published later.

The main results presented here represent two schools designated as the "pilot project." The experience gained will be applied to the other schools the project will serve.

4.1 Participants

The first activity involved presenting and encouraging the participation of schools:

- In March 2022, visits and meetings were conducted with the directors and teachers of two municipal schools to clarify and organize the project.
- In April, workshops were conducted with the teachers on Maker Culture, Prototyping, and Additive Manufacturing at the Maker Space on the Cariacica campus.
- From April to September, workshops were conducted with the students on Maker Culture, Prototyping, and Additive Manufacturing at the Maker Space on the Cariacica campus.
- The project reached two schools, involving 12 teachers and 167 students.

4.2 Comments

The project sparked the development of new skills among those involved:

- For students: Skills in Programming, Computer-Aided Design, Data Analysis, and Interpersonal Relationships.
- For teachers and school principals: Awareness of the relevance of maker culture and active learning methods in schools.

The experience demonstrated how the introduction of new technologies in the lives of elementary school students sparked an interest in seeking new knowledge and a vision of new opportunities for educational, personal, and professional development. Students designed and printed their product ideas (gifts, toys). This opportunity also awakened skills in some students that they still needed to develop. The project also involved the participation of students with specific learning needs, such as Autism and Down Syndrome.

The activities throughout the project showed how Maker Culture, especially 3D Printing, is accessible and viable for fostering and stimulating the interest of students and teachers, promoting more participatory classes.

Regarding campus scholarship students, it was observed how the integration of knowledge about Additive Manufacturing not only created a new perspective on work through new technologies, expanding the vision of opportunities for the use of Additive Manufacturing-related tools, but also stimulated the use of this technology in the development and application of both technical and Core Curriculum disciplines in their courses of study.

5 Final Remarks

It is important to emphasize that this research outcome is part of a project that began in 2022. It has limitations, and new data and information will be presented in subsequent publications.

Continuing with the project, the aim is to capture the potential transformative experiences among the research participants.

For the community served, represented by the schools, the Maker Space at IFES Cariacica will remain accessible as a reference center for rapid prototyping, 3D printing, dissemination of maker culture, and encouragement of PBL practices.

6 References

- Anderson, Chris (2012). *Makers: the new industrial revolution*. Crown Business. New York.
- Todos pela educação (2018). *Anuário Brasileiro da Educação Básica*, 2018. São Paulo: Moderna, 2018.
- Braga, M.; Guerra, A; Reis, J.C.O. Breve história da ciência moderna: convergência de saberes. Rio de Janeiro: Zahar.
- Campos, L. C. (2011). *Aprendizagem baseada em projetos: uma nova abordagem para a Educação em Engenharia*. COBENGE, SC.
- Cupani, A. (2016). *Filosofia da tecnologia: um convite*. 3.ed. Florianópolis: Editora da UFSC.
- Eychenne, F.; Neves, H. (2013). *Fab Lab: a vanguarda da nova revolução industrial*. Fab Lab Brasil.
- Gershenfeld, Neil (2007). *FAB: the coming revolution on your desktop - from personal computers to personal fabrication*. Nova York: Basic Books.
- Gil, A.C (2010). *Como elaborar projetos de pesquisa*. 5.ed. São Paulo: Atlas.
- Igoe, T.; Mota, C (2011). *A strategist's guide to digital fabrication*. *Strategy + Business*, Issue 64-Autumn.
- Lakatos, E. M.; Marconi, M. A (2013). *Metodologia do Trabalho Científico*. 7° ed. São Paulo: Atlas.
- Martinez, S.L.; Stager, G (2013). *Invent to learn making, tinkering, and engineering in the classroom*. Torrence, CA: Constructing Modern Knowledge Press.
- Mattar, F.N (2001). *Pesquisa de marketing: uma orientação aplicada*. 3.ed. Porto Alegre: Bookman.
- Markham, T.; Larmer, J.; Ravitz (2008). *J. Aprendizagem Baseada em Projetos*. Artmed Editora S/A, Porto Alegre.
- Masson, T. J.; Miranda, L. F.; Munhoz Jr, A. H.; Castanheira, A. M. P (2012). *Metodologia de Ensino: aprendizagem baseada em projetos (PBL)*. In: *XL Congresso Brasileiro de Educação em Engenharia, COBENGE*, Belém – PA.
- Ribeiro, L. R.; Mizukami, M.G.N (2004). *A PBL na Universidade de Newcastle: um modelo para o Ensino de Engenharia no Brasil?* Universidade Estadual de Ponta Grossa, Ponta Grossa.
- Roslund, S.; Rodgers, E.P (2014). *Makerspaces*. Ann Arbor, MI: Cherry Lake Publishing.
- Santos, M.; Becker, B. K. (orgs) (2007). *Território, territórios: ensaios sobre o ordenamento territorial*.
- Thiollent, M (1998). *Metodologia da pesquisa-ação*. 4.ed. São Paulo: Cortez: Autores Associados.
- Troxler, P. (2010). *Commons-Based Peer-Production of Physical Goods: Is There Room for a Hybrid Innovation Ecology?* (October 8, 2010). Paper presented at the *3rd Free Culture Research Conference*, Berlin, October 8-9, 2010. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1692617> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1692617>.
- Vergara, S. C. (2016). *Métodos de pesquisa em Administração*. 2.ed. São Paulo. Atlas.